

ATHLETICS - THE QUEEN OF SPORT. EFFECTS OF ACTIVITIES ATHLETICS FOR FUNCTIONAL AND THE PHYSICAL STATE OF THE HUMAN

Ubbiev Baxit Amangeldievich

Associative professor of the Department of Interfaculty Physical Culture
Karakalpak State University after named Berdakh
Nukus, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *The article deals with the history and development of athletics, its types and the reasons why the sport is called "Queen". The impact of athletics on the human body is to change the activity of the cardiovascular, respiratory systems, musculoskeletal system. Positive effects of sports lead to overall positive results in the level of health, functional and physical condition of the person.*

Keywords— physical activity, health, athletics, organism, sport, exercises, physical culture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many people today ask the question: why exactly athletics is called the queen of sports? In order to answer this question, you need to turn to the history of sports. After all, there are such types of sports activities, which have not lost their relevance for over 2000 years. It was athletics that was given such a flattering status. It is known that even in ancient times, such exercises were used to improve the physical training of soldiers. This sport was included in the program of the most the first Olympic Games, which were held in Ancient Greece in 776 BC.

In our era, athletics is also a constant "participant" in all kinds of competitions. Back in the 18-19 centuries, significant records were recorded in various areas of this sport. It is officially believed that the beginning of modern running competitions was laid in 1837 in various educational institutions in England. Later, short-distance running, throwing the nucleus, long jumping, running with obstacles, race walking was added to them and much more.

In 1865, the London Athletic Club was founded in the capital of England, thanks to which athletics became more and more popular.

This effect was reinforced by the emergence of the Amateur Athletic Association, which united all the small organizations in this country. Further, athletics, the queen of sports, came to the United States. An athletic club there was organized in 1868 in New York. After that, the "fashion" for athletics came to many other countries, where various organizations and clubs also began to form. a Since 1896, when the Olympic Games were revived, athletics has become widespread -after all, remembering the very first Olympics, the organizers gave her a leading role in the new version of the competition.

Athletics began to spread in Russia since 1888, when the first running sports club appeared in the vicinity of St. Petersburg. Since then, athletics has not been forgotten and has always been present in the lists of disciplines of prestigious

sports competitions. Traditionally, athletics includes running, walking, jumping and throwing, which are subdivided into the following disciplines:

- cross-country types;
- race walking;
- technical types (jumping and throwing);
- all-around;
- runs (running on the highway);
- cross-country runs (cross-country running).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

As a result of the competition, the winner is chosen, who can be both the athlete and the team that showed the best result. Athletes and sportswomen can start doing track and field athletics from the very tender age - 5-6 years. The earlier the child starts to play this sport, the more likely that he will achieve success in it.

This is perhaps the most popular sport - today track and field athletics is popular among both girls and boys. The International Association of Athletics Federations, operating since 1912, unites more than 200 national federations.

Running is not a pleasant activity for many. But as practice shows, it is the most optimal, cheapest way to keep track of your

health. Everyone runs: children, adults, old people with their dogs ...

Running can be used to achieve very different goals, from spiritual self-improvement to weight loss. Each person, if desired, will find the answer to his question with the help of running. But there are several basic processes that are stimulated during running - both a beginner and an experienced athlete should be aware of this.

1. During and after running, the process of hematopoiesis is activated - "young", healthy blood is formed.

2. Respiration is activated, absorption of free electrons from the air by the body is stimulated. An increase in the number of free electrons increases performance (physical and mental) and stimulates all human functions and systems.

3. During running, the production of carbon dioxide by the body is activated, which has a very beneficial effect on all biochemical processes occurring in cells. In particular, the amount of

oxygen, which helps to improve metabolism in the body.

4. During a run of average duration (30-60 minutes), the breakdown of cells is activated in the body, which, in turn, stimulates the synthesis of new young and healthy cells. With the help of running, the whole body is rejuvenated and renewed.

5. An adult's body contains approximately 35 liters of fluid (5 liters of blood, 2 liters of lymph and 28 liters of intracellular fluid). With a sedentary lifestyle, all this fluid stagnates. While running

the liquid begins to actively circulate, eliminating stagnant zones in the body.

7. During the run, the hormone serotonin is released, which is known to everyone as the hormone of happiness, thanks to which the mood improves, the symptoms of depression disappear, and tension is relieved.

The cardiovascular system is the first to receive a healing impulse when jogging. According to experts, the heart and blood vessels are very they respond positively to unhurried loads of medium (30-60 minutes) duration. Classes on strength machines or with a barbell (dumbbells) develop skeletal muscles well, while absolutely not stimulating the development of the heart muscle and blood vessels. In contrast, running is considered one of the best ways to restore and maintain the cardiovascular system at the proper level.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Walking is the easiest of all sports. You don't need to spend a lot of energy on it, and the effect is quite high. Walking has a health-improving effect on the body, raises muscle tone, strengthens bone tissue, develops coordination of movements, and stimulates metabolism. This kind of physical activity can be considered the safest kind. Almost everyone can do it, from a teenager to an elderly person. Now it has gained incredible popularity in European countries and America as a means to combat physical inactivity and its attendant problems. A few years ago, an Irish health organization launched the Health Trail project, which aims to involve as many of the population as possible in walking. Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Canada and Germany have already joined this project. In Germany, on certain days, mass walks are organized, in which thousands of people participate.

Brisk walking is also good with a reduced emotional background, depressed, depressed mood. In the process of walking, just as with other loads (running, swimming, etc.), the

body produces endorphins - hormones that have a positive effect on the psyche.

Over time, the habit of walking quickly can become motor automatism, especially if you use known routes of movement. There are no contraindications for walking, even a hypertensive person can deal with it. It is recommended to practice it for many diseases of the cardiovascular, pulmonary systems, for nervous overstrain and even during rehabilitation periods. It has a strengthening effect on literally the entire body.

The positive influence of physical development on mental development was known in China, even in the days of Confucius, in ancient Greece, India, and Japan. In the monasteries of Tibet and Shaolin, physical exercise and labor were taught

on a par with theoretical disciplines. Also in Ancient Greece: Plato was a two-time Olympic champion in pankration (mixed style of martial arts), Pythagoras was a champion in fist fights and this did not prevent them to be and remain refined intellectuals.

How and why physical activity improves mental health is currently not fully understood. Some theories, for example, look at the effects of exercise on various hormones and other chemicals in our body.

A decrease in the level of mental excitability and depression and an improvement in the general condition that occur as a result of a physically active life will certainly have a positive effect on the performance of their professional duties by those whose work is mainly related to mental activity.

For many students and knowledge workers, this, first of all, means that the time spent on physical education will never be wasted. On the contrary, even a 30-minute workout will increase mental capacity and more efficient use of time.

4. CONCLUSION

This article reviewed several examples of the impact of athletics exercises on the human body. According to the given data, it is enough for a person to perform elementary physical activity, to improve your health and stay fit. With regular exercise, you can resist the endless stream of stress, anxiety and depression that is so common in this century. Physical activity can act as a kind of protective buffer that reduces stress and stress of everyday life, as well as positively affecting the improvement of mood and the general physical and psychological state of a person.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Barchukov I.S. Physical culture: textbook. allowance. - M.: Unity-Dana, 2003.
- [2] Zhilkin A.I., Kuzmin V.S. Athletics. - M., 2005.
- [3] Ponomarev NI The emergence and initial development of physical education. - M., 1970.